

HLS code transformation strategies and directives exploration for FPGA accelerated ECG analysis

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Abstract—Electrocardiogram analysis has been established as a key factor for analysing and assessing the health status of a person. The ECG analysis flow is complex, relies on machine learning algorithms such as Support Vector Machines classifier and in an effort to be executed in real-time Hardware acceleration is required. In this paper we focus on utilizing High Level Synthesis capabilities to produce efficient SVM hardware accelerators, targeting ECG analysis. Our case study is arrhythmia detection using MIT-BIH ECG signal medical database. We show that as a first step, the original code under acceleration can be re-structured in order to create instances which are efficiently transformed into a HW accelerator. As a second step, an exploration is performed on the transformed code in order to determine which HLS directives produce the best outcome in terms of various performance and resources utilization metrics. Our combined analysis shows that we can achieve results of up to 94% execution latency gain compared to the original SVM code and the designer is provided with the infrastructure necessary in order to decide the best trade-off between gains in latency versus increase in utilized FPGA HW resources.

I. INTRODUCTION

One of the most fundamental and crucial biological signals for monitoring and assessing the health status of a person is the Electrocardiogram (ECG) due to its inherent relation to heart physiology [6]. Consequently, its analysis and interpretation has been established as an important field in modern medicine and this in turn has spawned various inter-disciplinary studies including digital processing analysis of the signal. Recently, machine learning techniques have dominated ECG analysis given the complexity to derive exact models in the effort of assessing and predicting the state of the heart. Support Vector Machines [5] based classifiers have grown very popular as the key element of machine learning based ECG analysis due to their capability of accurate prediction. In addition, constant monitoring and real-time heart condition assessment have imposed new requirements for acceleration and low power execution of a digital ECG analysis flow. In this work, we focus on Arrhythmia [1] detection in a real-time operating ECG analysis flow.

Support vector Machines are widely used as classifiers in many systems and there is much work in their incorporation in ECG arrhythmia detection flows [3]. The popularity behind these classifiers is twofold; on the one hand they exhibit very high classification accuracy even in problems which exhibit complex non-linear distribution in the extracted features space and on the other hand, their structure, based on stencil computation operations forms a perfect candidate for applying acceleration techniques. This has been shown in [4] which have proven that when the classification problem becomes very complex and the computational requirements of SVM classifier are multiplied HW acceleration can be the key for meeting the time and power constraints of the ECG

signal analysis flow. Towards this direction, they propose a custom HW architecture with which the algorithm is efficiently accelerated.

Hardware acceleration is a fundamental technique for creating systems which execute complex algorithms efficiently with reduced power budget constraints. However, designing a HW accelerator in HDL can be a time consuming and difficult to debug task. An approach on mitigating these issues is High Level Synthesis [8] where the functional description of an algorithm in the form of a C function are automatically translated into a hardware description. A HW accelerator in the majority of the cases is more efficient compared to an HLS defined one however HLS enables very quick HW implementation and exploration of a variety of architectural characteristics which is extremely difficult to achieve in HDL in a small amount of time. This is why HLS is ever increasingly utilized as HW design mechanism either for architectural exploration of fast prototype.

What is important to state is that available tools utilized in creating an HLS originate HW accelerator are not always capable of producing the best possible solution due to limitations in their analysis of the structure of the code. We have identified this problem and as a part of this work, we propose two strategies of manually restructuring the original code under acceleration to assist the HLS flow to fully utilize the inherent parallelisation capabilities of the algorithms. These strategies have proven to be capable of producing very high gains in latency by only a small sacrifice in hardware resources. On top of these manual configurations we apply directives which are the HLS infrastructure to explore different architectural options and we examine how these directives affect the produced accelerator.

The paper is organised as follows. Sections II and III present background information regarding the presented use case i.e. ECG based arrhythmia detection and Support Vector Machines classifier. Section IV summarizes the key points of the methodology of efficiently building the accelerator, especially focusing on the code restructuring strategies (Sections IV-1 and IV-2) and how they affect the various metrics and the employed HLS directives (Section IV-A). Section V provides the experimental results of the application of the aforementioned HLS directives and Section VI concludes the paper.

II. MOTIVATION

Arrhythmia, i.e irregular heartbeat is considered as one of the most commonly encountered heart malfunctions. Taking

into account the severity of a person exhibiting arrhythmia incidences, the field of detecting signs of arrhythmia in an ECG signal has been highly investigated, mostly being based on machine learning solutions [11]. Since machine learning solutions require a rich data set to be used for their training, there is a number of open data-based including ECG signals. A well-known and rather frequently used database as such is the MIT-BIH Arrhythmia Database [2] a combined effort of MIT and Beth Israel Deaconess Medical Center. This database is composed of 48 fully annotated half-hour two-lead ECG signals with the collaboration of patients from different medical files and physiology characteristics. Additionally, all the signals of this database have been annotated by medical experts thus forming an ideal starting point for creating a training data set for the detection problem. The process of acquiring and processing an ECG signal is composed of various stages with distinct characteristics and requirements. A simplified overview of this processing flow is depicted in Fig. 1 where the following key features are included:

- **Noise removal:** the signal is filtered, usually using a band-pass filter in order to remove artifacts resulting from patient breathing and movement and noise imported by the power line.
- **R peak detection:** An R peak [7] is a special point in each heart beat which is used for the new heart beat detection. In a real-time ECG acquisition system, the heart beat is not known a priori and points of interest such as the R peak have to be defined in order for a new heart beat to be identified.
- **Feature extraction process:** Having determined a new heart beat, a feature extraction process is imposed on it in order to extract its characteristics. In this work, we utilized Discrete Wavelet Transformation [3] as the core of the feature extraction process.
- **Diagnosis classification:** The final stage of the analysis flow is actually detecting whether the heart beat exhibits arrhythmia signs or not. This is performed using a classification algorithm, which detects the pattern of problematic beat. This employed classification as a part of this work is the Support Vectors Machine classifier and the main focus of this work is creating a HW accelerator which speeds up its execution.

Fig. 1: Utilized ECG analysis flow

III. BACKGROUND INFORMATION ON SVM CLASSIFIER

Support Vector Machines (SVMs) in machine learning are supervised learning models that are used for data classification and are suitable only for binary classification problems. The classification process requires that the data is separated into training and testing test. The instances in the training set have

the form of a feature vector consisting of the attributes that are being observed and a label indicating the class each instance belongs to. The instances in the testing set consist only of the attributes. The goal of the SVM classification technique is to train a model that can predict the label (class) of an instance of the testing set given only the attributes of the corresponding instance. In the presented case study, the feature vectors derive from a heart beat under analysis and the training labels have been provided by medical experts.

This goal is met thanks to the ability of the SVM to find a hyperplane that divides samples into two classes with the widest margin between them. A mapping function is used to project each feature vector of the training set to a feature space of higher dimension where the data will be easier to classify. The SVM is used to find the optimal hyperplane for classifying the data according to their attributes. This optimal hyperplane maximizes the distance between the hyperplane and the feature vectors that belong to each class and are closest to the hyperplane. These feature vectors closest to the hyperplane represent the decision boundary between the classes and are called support vectors. The distance between support vectors and a feature vector from the testing set is used to classify the new feature vector. The function that is used for computing the distance between this unclassified feature vector and the support vectors by firstly projecting them to a higher dimensional feature space is called kernel function. The hyperplane decision function for classifying feature vector \mathbf{x} is of the following form:

$$Class = \text{sgn}\left(\sum_{i=1}^{N_{sv}} (y_i * a_i * K(\mathbf{x}, \text{sup_vector}_i)) - b\right) \quad (1)$$

where K is the kernel function, \mathbf{x} is the feature vector, sup_vector_i is the i -th support vector and y_i, a_i are values related to it and result from the classifier training process. Coefficient b is a bias value, also a result of the training process and is constant over all support vectors.

The kernel function is very important to the accurate prediction of testing data and thus different kernel functions provide the acceptable classification accuracy depending on the dataset. The most popular kernels are linear ones, polynomial, sigmoid and Radial Basis Function (RBF). In this paper RBF is the chosen kernel since biomedical applications have proved to perform poorly when linear kernels are used with medical datasets, which are characterized by non linear relations between the attributes. The advantage of the RBF kernel over the other non linear kernels is that RBF has fewer parameters and fewer numerical difficulties. The RBF kernel for two vectors \mathbf{a} and \mathbf{b} is defined as:

$$K(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) = \exp(-\gamma \|\mathbf{a} - \mathbf{b}\|^2) \quad (2)$$

The combination of equations (1) and (2) provide us the final decision function (3) which will be the target of the HW acceleration process:

$$Class = \text{sgn}\left(\sum_{i=1}^{N_{sv}} (y_i * a_i * \exp(-\gamma \| \mathbf{x} - \text{sup_vector}_i \|^2)) - b\right) \quad (3)$$

Listing 1, provides the actual implementation of equation (3) in a C-language based form and this code will be used as the basis for the implementation of HLS based HW accelerator.

```

1 const float sv_coef[N_sv];
2 const float sup_vectors[D_sv][N_sv];
3
4 float SVM_predict (float test_vector[D_sv]) {
5
6 loop_i:for (i=0; i<N_sv; i++){
7   loop_j:for (j=0; j<D_sv; j++){
8     diff=test_vector[j]-sup_vectors[j][i];
9     norma = norma + diff*diff;
10  }
11  sum = sum + exp(-gamma*norma)*sv_coef[i];
12  norma=0;
13 }
14
15 sum = sum - b;
16
17 if (sum<0)
18   *y = -1;
19 else
20   *y = 1;
21
22 return y;
23 }

```

Listing 1: SVM original prediction code

In Listing 1 *sv_coef* stands for the product of y_i and α_i of equation 1. The reader should observe that the number of the support vectors N_{sv} and the length of the feature vector D_{sv} along with the kernel selected have a great impact on classifier complexity. In the presented case study, the training phase resulted in N_{sv} equal to 1274 and D_{sv} equal to 18.

IV. CODE RESTRUCTURING FOR HLS

High-level synthesis (HLS) software tools are capable of taking an input C program and generating effective RTL with performance that meets the user’s goals. However, often additional efforts are still required in complement to Vivado-HLS [10] capabilities to get the best performance. In this section we explore transformations of the initial code in that direction.

We emphasize on two code restructuring strategies which if employed assist the tool to produce much more efficient hardware accelerators. At the first one the original code is partitioned in more functional blocks in order for them to be executed in parallel. This function is not inherently supported with a directive in HLS but it is highly efficient should the programmer take care to enable such structure. Since big parallel chunks of execution take place at the same time we refer to this technique as coarse grain parallelism. The second technique, focuses on executing loops of calculation in a tree-based structure so that more parallelism in the level of instructions is exhibited. This functionality is supported by directives, however restructuring the code can result in better gains compared to what the tool is able to infer on its own.

1) *Advancing Coarse Level Parallelism in HLS:* At first we try to increase the parallelism on function level. In the code in Listing 1 *test_vector* represents the feature vector to be classified. It is implemented as an array of D_{sv} elements, as many as the attributes of interest are. Array *sup_vectors* has N_{sv} columns, one for each support vector, and each column-support vector has D_{sv} elements-attributes. According to the decision function, there are no data dependencies between the computations performed between the test vector and each column of the support vector’s array. As a result, these computations can be performed simultaneously.

This is the main idea of this parallelization technique. Array support vectors can be partitioned into smaller arrays, each one containing fewer support vectors. These arrays will have the same number of rows, since the number of attributes does not change, but fewer columns. Each array will contribute a partial sum to the total sum used for classification. The calculations needed for the partial sums to be computed can be performed in parallel. We have thus managed to divide the initial large problem into smaller ones, which are then solved at the same time. Each smaller problem is not a subtask of the initial task but the same task performed on a smaller dataset. All the small problems are processed independently at the same time and their results are combined for the final computations. Thus, we have accomplished to extract coarse level parallelism from the initial problem.

Firstly, we are presenting the changes to the code needed. The main part of the code that is responsible for computing the total sum is going to be implemented as a separate function called by the main function as many times as many array partitions exist. Each instance of this function computes the partial sum that each array contributes to the total sum. The main function gathers the partial sums and makes the classification decision.

Initially, the goal was to perform array partitioning automatically using HLS directives. An array in HLS is implemented using block RAMs which can at most have two read ports. This means that the simultaneous computation among all the array partitions wouldn’t be possible since all functions would require access to the same array at the same time. By partitioning the support vector array we have different read ports for each partition and the parallelization is possible.

Array *sup_vectors* is automatically partitioned across the column dimension into a varying number of partitions and each partition will contain consecutive columns (block partitioning). In the main function we call the function once for each array partition passing as argument the pointer to the support vectors array and the columns each function is going to operate on. Then the dataflow directive is applied on the main function and allows functions within scope of the main function to operate in parallel. HLS automatically detects that the function calls can be executed simultaneously and completes the allocation of resources and synthesis accordingly. In listing 2 you can see the modified code and the directives added for the case that the support vector array is partitioned into two smaller ones:

```

1 const float sv_coef[N_sv];
2 const float sup_vectors[D_sv][N_sv];
3
4 void SVM_partial_predict(int width, int offset,
5     float *sum, float test_vector[D_sv], float
6     sv_coef[N_sv], float sup_vectors[D_sv][N_sv]){
7     int i, j;
8     float diff, norma=0;
9     *sum=0;
10
11 loop_i:for (i=0; i<width; i++){
12     loop_j:for (j=0; j<D_sv; j++){
13         diff=test_vector[j]-sup_vectors[j][i+offset];
14         norma = norma + diff*diff;
15     }
16     *sum = *sum + exp(-gamma*norma)*sv_coef[i+offset
17 ];
18     norma=0;
19 }
20 float SVM_predict (float test_vector[D_sv]) {
21 #pragma HLS ARRAY_PARTITION
22 variable=sup_vectors block factor=2 dim=2
23 #pragma HLS DATAFLOW
24 float diff, sum1, sum2, sum;
25
26 SVM_partial_predict(N_sv/2, 0, &sum1, test_vector,
27     sv_coef, support_vectors);
28 SVM_partial_predict(N_sv/2, N_sv/2, &sum2,
29     test_vector, sv_coef, support_vectors);
30 sum = sum1 + sum2 - b;
31
32 if (sum<0)
33     *y = -1;
34 else
35     *y = 1;
36
37 return y;
38 }

```

Listing 2: Partitioned version of the original code

Experiments involving automatic partitioning have shown that as far as latency is concerned, when more partitions are being processed in parallel less cycles are needed for the classification to conclude. In fact the speedup is almost equal to the number of the array partitions. There is however a trade-off between the gain in latency and the increasing area resources. In order for the function instances to run in parallel the logic used for the function body is duplicated. This explains the increase in DSP, flip flop and LUT utilization. For array partitioning of factor 16 we can see a burst in all the resources utilization and especially in BRAM, which is attributed to internal decisions of the HLS compiler.

In our efforts to prevent this burst from happening, we tried to apply the same idea only this time doing it manually. The only thing that differs from the previous implementation is the way the support vector array is partitioned. Instead of declaring one large array and then partitioning it into smaller ones using the array partitioning directive, we allocate several smaller arrays from the start. Now in each function call a different array pointer is passed pointing to one of the array partitions. This means that we must manually split the array containing the support vectors into smaller arrays containing fewer support vectors. The results are shown in Fig. 2:

We noted that the gain in latency is even greater now, giving as a speedup very close to the ideal speedup that equals with the number of partitions executing in parallel. This is depicted in Fig. 3. The increase in area resources remains the same,

Fig. 2: Latency gain vs number of partitions (manual)

except for the burst in number of BRAMs when partitioning for a factor of 16 which is now remedied.

Fig. 3: Speedup gain comparison (automatic vs manual)

2) *Advancing Instruction Level Parallelism through arithmetic operation reshaping*: So far we have explored how to parallelize the SVM classifier on coarse level by performing the computations related to different support vectors simultaneously. Now we are going to examine increasing parallelism in the required computations for calculating the contribution of one support vector only. We are going to parallelize the inner loop (loop_j) of the code on instruction level, which is responsible for the computation of the euclidean distance.

Each time this loop is executed it computes the euclidean distance between a different support vector and the test vector to be classified. Instead of computing one squared difference in each iteration we could compute several of them at the same time. This is achieved by the loop being unrolled, storing each squared difference in a temporary variable and ultimately adding all of them to the variable holding the final distance.

Adding many floating point values in HLS increases dramatically the critical path because the additions occur in a serial manner even though there is no true data dependency between the added values. However a more efficient implementation of the addition is feasible by changing the structure of the addition and transforming it into a tree-based computation of the final result. That way HLS can schedule the independent calculations to be executed in parallel allocating if needed more hardware resources.

The classifier which was determined as the best for the arrhythmia detection has a feature vector of 18 attributes so this is also the number of iterations of the inner loop. We have applied the above idea by manually unrolling the inner loop by a factor of 3, 6 and 18. Several changes have to be made to the code in Listing 1.

Firstly, more differences are being computed (as many as the unroll factor is) and saved to temporary variables. HLS allocates different hardware resources for most operations in the loop body so these subtractions can be executed simultaneously. Then each one of the computed differences is raised to the power of two. These multiplications are also performed in parallel. Then we begin to add the squared differences following a tree-based structure, adding them in pairs to produce new temporary values. Accordingly, these values have to be added again in pairs and this continues until all the squared differences have been added to the variable containing the euclidean distance on loop completion. In listing 3 the above strategy is demonstrated using an unroll factor of 6.

```

1 const float sv_coef[N_sv];
2 const float sup_vectors[D_sv][N_sv];
3
4 float SVM_predict (float test_vector[D_sv]) {
5 loop_i:for (i=0; i<N_sv; i++) {
6 loop_j:for (j=0; j<D_sv; j=j+6) {
7 d1=test_vector[j]-sup_vectors[j][i];
8 d2=test_vector[j+1]-sup_vectors[j+1][i];
9 d3=test_vector[j+2]-sup_vectors[j+2][i];
10 d4=test_vector[j+3]-sup_vectors[j+3][i];
11 d5=test_vector[j+4]-sup_vectors[j+4][i];
12 d6=test_vector[j+5]-sup_vectors[j+5][i];
13
14 sq_prod1=d1*d1;
15 sq_prod2=d2*d2;
16 sq_prod3=d3*d3;
17 sq_prod4=d4*d4;
18 sq_prod5=d5*d5;
19 sq_prod6=d6*d6;
20
21 tmp_sum1=sq_prod1+sq_prod2;
22 tmp_sum2=sq_prod3+sq_prod4;
23 tmp_sum3=sq_prod5+sq_prod6;
24 tmp_sum4=tmp_sum1+tmp_sum2;
25
26 norma = norma + tmp_sum3;
27 norma = norma + tmp_sum4;
28 }
29
30 sum = sum + exp(-gamma*norma)*sv_coef[i];
31 norma=0;
32 }
33
34 sum = sum - b;
35
36 if (sum<0)
37 *y = -1;
38 else
39 *y = 1;
40
41 return y;

```

TABLE I: Evaluated metrics for automatic vs manual unrolling

Version	Unroll factor	Automatic Unroll using directives					Manual Unroll using tree structure				
		latency (cycles)	BRAM (%)	DSP (%)	FF (%)	LUT (%)	latency (cycles)	BRAM (%)	DSP (%)	FF (%)	LUT (%)
initial	-	412783	24	20	3	11	412783	24	20	3	11
unrolled	3	252259	24	21	3	11	214039	47	26	4	14
unrolled	6	206395	24	23	3	11	149065	70	34	5	18
unrolled	18	173271	27	20	3	11	90461	27	50	8	29

Listing 3: Unrolled version of the original code

In Table I we can see the difference between applying the unroll directives on the inner loop and manually unrolling it while using a tree-based expression balancing structure for the computations.

There is a significant improvement in latency gain when applying manual unrolling compared to the automatic unrolling and the difference becomes greater the larger the unrolling factor is. The reason behind that is the tree based structure of the computations that allows data independent operations to execute in parallel.

Manual loop unrolling causes also an increase in BRAM utilization for most unroll factors. When unrolling for a factor of 3, three accesses at array support vectors are required at the same time. To achieve this, HLS creates a copy of the array and implements both copies using dual port RAMs since three elements can be read from four ports. There is a gain in parallelism and latency but the BRAMs utilization doubles. In case of unrolling for a factor of 6, three copies of the same array are needed to be implemented with dual port rams in order for parallelism to be achieved. Thus BRAM utilization triples. When fully unrolling the loop however, HLS automatically partitions the array in 18 rows implemented as dual port ram each, and as a result parallelism is possible without memory increase.

The memory increase problem can be avoided altogether by applying array partition directives, as discussed in the next section. An increase in the DSP utilization is also observed. The explicit declaration of parallel subtractions and multiplications as well as of the parallel additions of the tree structure result in an increase in the instances and thus in DSPs. HLS allocates more DSPs to achieve parallelism and tries to maximize sharing during the scheduling and binding process. Utilization of flip flops and LUTs is also increased due to increase in instances, multiplexers and registers.

A. Exploration of HLS Directives

In the previous sections we examined ways to create effective RTL that were based on structural modifications of the C code. These modifications make up a first level of optimization that brings to RTL satisfactory efficiency. The performance though can be further improved by combining these structural modifications with the HLS directives. In this section we are going to explore the impact the chosen directives can have on the efficiency of the accelerator.

The directives chosen for optimization differ from one application to another and depend on the nature of the algorithm. For the SVM classifier the selection of directives

Fig. 4: Impact of directives in `loop_i`

applied is based on the instruction level parallelism that can be accomplished. Most of the directives used, aim at optimizing the inner loop that computes the euclidean distance between the test and support vector.

As mentioned before, the squared differences that compose the euclidean distance can be computed in parallel, which means that we should unroll the inner loop. For an unrolling factor greater than two this leads to more than two simultaneous reads to the same array. As a result we have to change the array structure by partitioning or reshaping so as to have more read ports and the accesses to the required elements can happen in parallel. In the same manner we can unroll the outer loop and partition or reshape the arrays accessed in each iteration of the outer loop to gain parallel access to their elements.

The directives applied on the classifier are **Loop pipeline**, **Loop unroll**, **Array partition** and **Array reshape**. They can be applied to any of the implementations mentioned at the previous sections since all of them maintain the same computational kernel regardless of any expression balancing or how large the dataset they operate on is.

We implemented four basic versions of the SVM classifier. The initial given in Listing 1 and three versions which had the inner loop manually unrolled by a factor of 3, 6 and 18 (fully unrolled) respectively as described in section IV-2. These implementations were synthesized for all valid combinations of the directives above for various values of their parameters. Some combinations were excluded due to directives incompatibility (for example pipeline unrolls all loops down its hierarchy so there is no point in combining these two directives) and others due to user defined constraints.

For the initial implementation the main constraint we applied was that there is no reason to partition an array without unrolling the loop in which it is accessed since in each iteration

there's only one access needed. When the corresponding loop is unrolled by some factor then the array is partitioned or reshaped by that same factor. Also when a computation requires the elements of two arrays and one of them is partitioned or reshaped the other must be too. In the implementations where the inner loop is already unrolled we loosen the first constraint. The arrays in the inner loop can be partitioned or reshaped when the inner loop is not further unrolled but by a factor equal to the factor the loop is already manually unrolled by.

V. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

In this section, the impact of specific directives on the various metrics is examined. Each of the Figs. 4 to 6 depict how all configurations score in metrics with one specific directive enabled or not. The utilized High Level Synthesis tool was Xilinx Vivado HLS (v2015.2) [10] targeting Zedboard Zynq Development kit xc7z020clg484-1 [9].

In Fig. 4a the pipeline directive in `loop_i` has been examined. Results show its definitive impact on latency since when it is applied gain between 90 and 100% is exhibited. It does lead however to a large critical path that often exceeds the time constraints. In terms of BRAM utilization, when the directive is applied, there is a wider range of utilization values varying from 20 to 120% but with the same median value compared to the opposite case. When applying this directive, DSP, Flip Flop and LUT utilization exhibit greater ranges and median value. Especially for DSPs, the range of values is wide, which is not the case for flip flops and LUTs. The higher values of the utilization of area resources, that sometimes even exceed the available resources, can be explained from the fact that when pipeline is applied to a loop, it unrolls all loops inside of it. This leads to an unavoidable increase in area.

Fig. 4b depicts the results of unrolling the outer loop (`loop_i`). Improvements in latency are observed and in par-

Fig. 5: Impact of directives in `loop_j`

particular the gain reaches a median value of 70%, although the range of values remains wide (from 40% to 100%). This improvement is attributed to the reduction of loop iterations and thus loop controls. When this directive is applied the BRAM utilization takes values starting from 20% and sometimes even exceeds the available resources. This happens due to the duplicate arrays that are created when the unroll directive is not combined with array partitioning. However, the median value is close to the BRAM utilization of the original. When the directive is not applied the BRAM utilization is very close to this median value with a dispersion less than 5%. As far as DSPs, FFs and LUTs utilization is concerned its value range is equally wide when the directive is applied and not, but the median value is greater upon its application. This is anticipated since when unrolling a loop HLS creates duplicates of the loop body and thus the area is increased.

When utilizing the pipeline directive in the inner loop (`loop_j`) latency gains have a narrower range and has a median value of 60% as shown in Fig. 5a. When the loop is not pipelined the range is much wider and even extends to negative values. The median value is close to 100% but this is thanks to the pipelining of the outer loop which cannot be combined with the pipelining of the inner loop and usually leads to a burst in memory resources utilization. When pipelining the inner loop all the area resources utilization is of much narrower range and is characterized by lower median values, close to the ones of the original version of the SVM code. This happens because pipeline increases parallelism by using all resources at all times and not by replicating hardware.

Unrolling the inner loop has a positive impact on latency gain as illustrated in Fig. 5b. The gain can take values from a wider range but the median value is 70% in comparison to the 40% of not applying this directive. The BRAMs, DSPs, FFs and LUT utilization has a similar range of values in both

cases but the median values are slightly greater when the inner loop is unrolled. This is again because unrolling a loop leads to replicating the loop body and thus to more logic and area.

In Fig. 6 we observe that partitioning an array does not have great effect on DSP, FF and LUT utilization. The range of values as well as the median value remain the same with small differences either the directive is applied or not. The latency gain is also in the same range and has the same median value. This is due to the fact that even when the array is not partitioned but the corresponding loop is unrolled, HLS creates duplicates of the arrays and reaches the same level of parallelism at the expense of BRAM utilization. When the array is not very large BRAM utilization is also not improved. However when the array is very large, like in the case of the array of support vectors, the range of values is restricted and the median value remains small. In particular when array support vectors is partitioned, it holds its initial median value of memory utilization. The same applies for the reshape directive. The only difference is that the median value of flip flop utilization is greater by a small percentage when the array is partitioned.

What is important apart from the exploration per directive is to understand and focus on the different architectural choices provided to the system designer in an effort of meeting different constraints and requirements. Towards this goal, in Fig. 7 we present the design space created by the different versions of manually restructured code which emphasized on unrolling `loop_j` a number of times and utilizing tree-structured performance of calculations (Section IV-A). All manually created versions of the code are explored with all aforementioned HLS directives for each one of them. The figure includes only designs which managed to achieve their clock target since we distinguish the opposite case as infeasible. The X axis is a combined and weighted value of the utilization in all available

(a) Impact of array partition cyclic directive in sup_vectors

(b) Impact of array reshape cyclic directive in sup_vectors

Fig. 6: Impact of directives in sup_vectors

metrics (BRAMs, DSPs, FFs and LUTs) while the Y axis is the estimated execution latency of the accelerator in ns derived from multiplying the required cycles for its execution with its operating frequency.

Fig. 7: Design space of HW accelerated SVM classifier

We can see that as indicated by the Pareto curve, there are many different non-dominated design choices which exhibit different characteristics. For example, optimum points in the left side of the design space exhibit the least HW resources utilization and fare relatively high on execution latency. As expected, such design points result from the original SVM code which is the least optimized and thus its execution is slow but its structure is simple thus requiring less resources. On the opposite side, the restructured versions of the code are on the right side of the figure meaning that they exhibit low execution latency and increased requirements in HW resources. This is derived from their more complex structure and

replicated functional units which enables parallel execution of calculations while imposing a toll on resources utilization.

VI. CONCLUSION

In this work we have presented a methodology for creating efficient HLS based HW accelerators targeting Support Vector Machine based classifiers. The methodology relies on two parts; first the original code under acceleration is transformed in order to assist the HLS tool to maximize the parallelization of the computational parts of the algorithm and secondly, on top of the produced code HLS combination directives are applied in order to explore a variety of architectural choices. Results of applying this methodology achieve up to 94% execution latency gain compared to the original SVM code while the impact on resource utilization remains adequately low for the accelerator to be synthesized on an FPGA.

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